

Nature and Extent of Crime Victimization: A Study on Urban Area in Bangladesh

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Abstract

This study has mainly explored the current nature and extent of crime victimization in urban areas in Bangladesh. It was exploratory in nature. The samples were selected randomly using a clustered sampling technique from 14 particular areas and respondents who were selected as victimized person or their household heads in this study. A structured and standardized survey questionnaire were used for data collection techniques and using SPSS statistical tools for analyzing data. The findings of the study are that the total number of the respondents was 3,957, among them most of them are female about 53% within 31% of victimized people. Their age ranging from 20 to 40 years, they have completed the primary and secondary level of education, their income below 20,000 and most of them are married and housewife by their occupation among them 8.5% got repeatedly victimized. As per the study findings, theft constitutes the highest number for victimization, where 79% and other types offences including snatching, sexual harassment, domestic violence and also other property related crime, snatching of things or properties, cheating, forgery, or any kind of fraudulent activity, threatening, and damage to property, rape etc were also be found in urban area. Most importantly, Dhaka north city has a higher victimization rate than the other cities in Bangladesh. In this study, it has found that about 95% of the respondents became victimized while living within their current address and most of the victims shared that the incident took place at the town mostly and the places of occurrence were mostly closed to the residence of the victims. The average distance of the place of occurrences and residences was about 4.6 km, and the nearest police station from the place of occurrence was 3.3 km on an average. The study also showed that most of the crimes have occurred within the mid hour of day time to the first hour of the night time, which starts from noon and ends 9 at night, and it constitutes 50 % of the total crime. Finally, it is also revealed that from January to April and November to December of 2018 were more crime-prone than the other months.

Keywords: Crime Victimization, Repeated Victimization, Crime Victim, Urban Area and Victimization Survey.

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1. Introductions and Background:

Crime victimization is the involuntary, personal exposure to criminal acts that can be economic, physical, psychological and emotional in nature. The measurement of nature and extent of crime victimization is very difficult because it is not exactly possible to find out how many people are victimized every year because a significant percentage of crimes remain unreported or undiscovered. By using the crime victimization statistics, the nature of crime victimization is revealed (Crime Victimization in the US: A Data-Driven Learning Guide, 2011). To explore the nature of crime victimization, it is needed to know about various

considering matter including characteristics of victim, characteristics of offenders, type of offence, whether the crime was reported to police, reasons the crime was or was not reported, and victim experiences with the criminal justice system etc. There are various types of offence including personal crimes including rape or sexual assault, robbery, aggravated and simple assault, and personal larceny and household property crimes including burglary/trespassing, motor vehicle theft, and other types of theft. The characteristics of victim and offenders are measured through their age, sex, race and Hispanic origin, marital status, education level, and income etc. On the other hand, characteristics of the crime including time and place of occurrence, use of weapons, nature of injury, and economic consequences are used to explain nature of crime victimization (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2019). In the United States, Uniform Crime Report (UCR) and National Crime Victimization Survey (NCVS) are the two largest and most comprehensive resources for information relating to crime and victimization. Two of these programs used for different purposes and these help researchers, policymakers, and the public with a general understanding regarding the state of crime and victimization or nature of victimization in the United States (www.ncjrs.gov, 2017)

In Bangladesh, crime victim and victimization is a tearing problem and some factors increase the visibility of victims and victimization including weakness of victim than offender, to be a female, sick, very old or very young and victim is blameless for what happened actually (Yesmen, 2019). Recently, urbanization has been going up at a higher rate than before in Bangladesh (World Bank Bangladesh development series-2007) and almost 35 million people live in urban areas and this 35 million is expected to exceed 80 million by 2030 (UN World Urbanization Prospect, 2007). Another study has shown that, recently the rise of urban crime, urban violent behavior and criminal activities or in a word urban victimization is increased than before because of this rural-urban migration (Khanam, 2016). In urban areas specially Dhaka has founded as a city of crime, insecurity and political violence, social unrest, violence, theft, robbery, looting, murder, hijacking, arson, throwing of acid on innocent females, raping of minor girls, possession and use of illegal arms, illegal rent/toll collection, frequent traffic congestion, etc. All of these crimes increased over the years and victimization in Dhaka is more common than other cities. (Siddiqui et al, 2000). A study also showed that a large number of people particularly women and children are becoming victims of various crimes including domestic violence, trafficking, acid burn, sexual harassment, and rape than the man because of their weakness characteristics (Sheikh, and Mamunur, 2013). Another study showed homeless adolescents are at also great risk for victimization and majority of them are become victims of physical torture and sexual harassment (Alam and Akter, 2017). There are many reasons behind crime victimization in urban areas such as massive degradation in the urban environment congestion, extreme pressure of housing, growth of slums and the pressure of urban services such as education, health, transportation, water, sanitation, electricity, fuel, garbage clearance, recreation and importantly their living below national poverty line etc. In Bangladesh, rapid urbanization leads some social problems such as floating population, slums, unemployment, drug addiction and violence and that leads crime victimization (Shafi, 2010).

Now, it is also apparent that researchers especially criminologists and sociologists attempted to get a deeper insight into the nature and extent of crime victimization in urban areas. So it can be easily said that nature of crime victimization in Bangladesh remains unexplored because of lack of study. If this situation is continuing the criminal justice system will be unable to protect society and offer the necessary assistance and the offenders or potential victims and offenders will also be suffered and it will be impossible to reduce the victimized rate (Doorewaard, 2014). It can also be argued that victimization surveys help to know about the nature and extent of crime that can help to reduce victims and offender sufferings through exploring the accurate nature of crime causation and victimization (Crime victimization survey in selected urban areas of Bangladesh, 2019). Therefore, it's necessary to know about the extent of crime to identify the reason why people are being victimized or not. For exploring the actual nature of crime victimization, three things must be considered firstly, victim perspectives, secondly, the offender perspectives and finally others situational perspectives including spatial analysis of crime, location and time of crime occurrence etc.

In this study, it has focused mainly the overall extent and nature of crime victimization in 14 urban areas including 12 city corporation areas and two other crime prone areas. This study quantifies nature of crime victimization through a systematic analysis from victimization surveys in selected urban areas over 2019 (Crime victimization survey in selected urban areas of Bangladesh, 2019). The main objective of this study was To identify the nature and magnitude of victimization in the selected urban areas by explaining their

social status, spatial analysis, time and location of being victimized and other prevalence. It also has revealed that how socio-demographic factors influences crime victim for being victimized. This study is exploratory in nature and samples are selected through randomly. Here data are collected from respondents who are being victimized of a crime or their household heads with a survey questionnaire. All of these data are explained through SPSS statistical tools.

2. Objectives of the Study:

In this study, it has tried to explore the extent of non-reporting or dark figure of crime and also relate crime victimization and dark figure of crime in highly crime prone urban areas including 12 City Corporation's areas (8 metropolitan areas) and also other two crime prone areas namely Bogra and Tangail. So the main research objectives of this study are:

1. To identify the prevalence of victimization in the selected urban areas.
2. To know about the gender based nature of victimization.
3. To learn about the city wise victimization information.
4. To learn about the spatial aspects of victimization and analysis.
5. To find out the place and time of victimization occurred.

3. Conceptual Framework:

4. Methodology:

Methodology is considered as a body of method, principles, rules and postulates employed by a specific discipline in a particular area of a study or activities. In 2002, Bowling defined methodology as a complete structure of overall processes or techniques that utilize to sample selection, data collection and analysis data (<https://nursinganswers.net/essays/the-definition-of-methodology-nursing-essay.php>). So from a methodological point of view, it can be cleared what types of research is conducted, who are the populations of that's study, how to select sample of that study and finally, what process would be used in data collection and data preparation phases.

4.1. Research Type:

This study is exploratory in nature because it has explored the dark figure of crime existing in Bangladeshi's society. Here in this study, it is important to note that exploratory research does not make sense for study areas with a lot of existing research and also it would be best suited to topics that have not been studied yet. So, during the early stages of a project or research area, exploratory research is conducted to test the feasibility of conducting a more extensive study.

4.2 Research Area:

This study has covered 14 city areas (including eight metropolitan areas and 12 city corporation areas). It is supposed that the city corporation areas have a higher propensity for crime victimization than the other cities. So it has been easy to find out the real drug figure of crime on those areas. Besides the city corporations areas, two spatially characterized cities have been selected, which have characteristics like higher population density, several industries, and higher population mobility rates, which make them more appropriate for the study.

4.3 Study Population:

In this study, crimes against property and crimes against persons have been characterized as Crimes. The study population is selected here as the crime victims who are at least 12 years old, have been victimized within the last 12 months (January 2018 – December 2018), whether they have reported the crime to the police or not, and they can explain the fact what researchers need for the study. Finally, the victim's household heads have also been selected as study population in the absence of the subject.

4.4 Sample Selection:

In this study, it has found that the selected cities were clustered according to distribution, and the number of wards was selected randomly using a clustered sampling technique from each city. All the households of the selected wards were treated as the sampling unit of the study. Households were selected from the wards by a systematic random sampling technique.

The sample size was determined by using the following formula, where the number of victims is not defined.

The following statistical formula is used to estimate the minimum sample size:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The sample size, } n &= \frac{z^2 p (1-p)}{d^2} \times def \\ &= \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(0.5)}{(0.02)^2} \times (1.5) \\ &= 3601 \end{aligned}$$

(3640 for equal distribution of respondents into selected areas)

Where n is the estimated minimum sample size

z = the value of standardized normal variate = 1.96 at 95% confidence level

p = Anticipated population proportion = 0.5

d = Absolute precision = 2%

def = Design effect = 1.5

As the size of the population is large, therefore, to ensure the validity and reliability, the original sample size has been determined by using design effect, 1.5. Considering, z=1.96, p=0.5, d=0.02; the minimum sample size is 3601. In order to minimize human errors and refusal of the respondents, the absolute precision level has been increased. In that case, the total sample size would be 3601. Therefore, a total of 3640 (for equal distribution into 14 cities) respondents statistically come up from the 8 division 14 cities, i.e., 260 from each city.

While approaching the respondents, the enumerators also looked for victims other than the respondents who first came in contact. As a result, other victims from the same household also were covered, which increased the total number of respondents. The current total number of respondents is 3,957. Multiple responses in the sense of multiple victimization information have also been considered in the study.

4.5 Data Collection:

This study has conducted with a structured and standardized survey questionnaire for data collection that includes both quantitative and qualitative information. The questionnaire was finalized incorporating all the feedback from the results of pre-tests. Here in the study, it has conducted to pre-testing the questionnaire to check and double-check the reliability and validity of the main research tool which will generate the findings. The questionnaire that was used for data collection was containing both open-ended and close-ended with multiple response options. A direct face-to-face interview technique with the completed questionnaire was used to effectively fulfill the study purpose. A total number of 3,957 respondents' information was collected while multiple responses found common in most of their responses.

4.6 Data Processing:

In this study, the quantitative data were processed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and Microsoft Excel software. Here, the qualitative data were coded and then tabulated. Finally, Data has analyzed with both descriptive and inferential statistical tools like frequency distribution, cross-tabulation, central tendency. Various types of statistical charts are used for the presentation of findings. Univariate, bivariate, and multivariate statistical analysis are used.

5. Findings:

The Nature and Extent of Crime Victimization

Spatial variations in levels of violence and the number of reported crimes at the police stations as well as the nature of crime and fear about it have been discussed in this section. The Prevalence of victimization shows the overall percentage of people becoming a victim of a crime which may also vary with time, months, location, etc.

1.1 Prevalence of the Victimization

The main objective of the study is to identify the nature and status of victimization in the selected urban areas. This study, without any prior information about the victim from any agency, has surveyed in 14 cities of Bangladesh, which are characterized as highly populated, have all the modern-day city facilities including education, health, residence as well as business sectors, offices, courts and government/nongovernment agencies. A standardized victimization survey has been conducted in these areas from where the following victimization information could have been found.

Figure 1: Prevalence of Crime Victimization in the Selected Urban Areas

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Victims

The total picture of the sample can be understood from the household data. Besides this, to get a more precise look into the victims' information, we have provided a brief description of the victims' demography here.

Firstly, the rate of women victimization is more than the male, as the data shows females constituted 53 percent and males 47 percent. The next question comes with their age. The study showed that the average age of the victims is about 36 years, where the minimum age considered for the study was 12, and the highest age of the victim was 86. The study also showed that about 60 percent of the victims were ranged

from 20 to 40 years of age. People from 40 to 50 years aged also had a significant victimization rate (about 17 percent).

Bangladesh has Muslim domination on its demography, which also was represented in the study as it showed about 90 percent of the victims were Muslim. The victims' educational background is essential because it influences their consciousness about the crime environment around them as well as the propensity to not fall for prey to crime. However, a strong correlation has been observed here in the case of victims' education level and rate of victimization. It is found from the study that about 74 percent of the victims had a less than graduation level of educational background, where 31 percent had secondary to higher secondary certificate degree. People with a higher education level had a less victimization rate (post-grad about 11% and grad about 15 percent). Kamruzzaman (2016) has showed the similar socio-demographic of respondents that have a relationship with victimization.

In terms of occupation, homemakers had the highest number of victimization (about 37 percent), business people had the next higher rate (about 20 percent) followed by service holders (17 percent). About 40 percent of the victims' income ranged from 10,000.00 to 20,000.00. The study also showed that people who have less than 40,000 taka as family income has a higher propensity to become the victim (about 77 percent). The data shows that people with a higher family income have a lower propensity to become a victim of crime.

■ **Summary of the Victims Demographic Information:**

- ✓ 59.4% of victims belonged to the age group 20 to 40 years.
- ✓ 53% of women experienced victimization in their life.
- ✓ 48.3% of the victims have completed the primary and secondary level of education.
- ✓ 36.8% of victims' occupation was a housewife.
- ✓ 76.1% of the victims were married.
- ✓ 48.1% of victims' monthly family income was below 20000 taka.

■ **The Situation of Repeat victimization**

The study shows that 1246 respondents out of 3957 got victimized within the last one year (From January 2018 to January 2019). According to the findings, more than one out of every four persons got victimized in the last year. Among the victims, the minimum re-victimization number is one and where the maximum number is 4, with an average of 1.11. The study also shows that 8.5 percent of the victims got repeatedly victimized with the highest number of 4. About 92 percent victimized at least once in the last year.

Figure 2: The Situation of Repeat Victimization

■ **1.2 Gender based Nature of Victimization**

Most of the victims faced theft (about 46 %), where females account for 58 % only for theft and 50% in all forms of crime. Among the females, 10% of females faced snatching, 5% faced cheating, 4% sexual harassment, about 5% domestic violence (94% among all). The next highest crime victims are snatching of things or properties which account for 10%. Cheating, forgery, or any kind of fraudulent activity constitutes 7.3%, threatening, and damage to property caused by 6% each, and the others are mainly different forms of property crimes. Few severe forms of crimes like domestic violence, rape have also been found, but the rate is low.

Table 1: Types of Crime Occurred vs. Gender of the Respondents

Crime Type (CT)		Gender of the Respondents (G)			Total
		Male	Female	3rd Gender	
Theft	Count	239	334	0	573
	% within CT	41.7%	58.3%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	40.8%	50.7%	0.0%	46.0%
Snatching	Count	62	69	0	131
	% within CT	47.3%	52.7%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	10.6%	10.5%	0.0%	10.5%
Dacoity	Count	18	20	0	38
	% within CT	47.4%	52.6%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	3.1%	3.0%	0.0%	3.0%
Extortion	Count	15	13	1	29
	% within CT	51.7%	44.8%	3.4%	100.0%
	% within G	2.6%	2.0%	100.0%	2.3%
Forgery	Count	15	5	0	20
	% within CT	75.0%	25.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	2.6%	0.8%	0.0%	1.6%
Cheating	Count	36	34	0	70
	% within CT	51.4%	48.6%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	6.1%	5.2%	0.0%	5.6%
Criminal Breach of Trust	Count	6	3	0	9
	% within CT	66.7%	33.3%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.7%
Bribery	Count	25	8	0	33
	% within CT	75.8%	24.2%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	4.3%	1.2%	0.0%	2.6%
Damage of Property	Count	37	37	0	74
	% within CT	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	6.3%	5.6%	0.0%	5.9%
Illegal Trespass	Count	6	5	0	11
	% within CT	54.5%	45.5%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.0%	0.8%	0.0%	0.9%
Illegal Confinement	Count	17	4	0	21
	% within CT	81.0%	19.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	2.9%	0.6%	0.0%	1.7%
Threatening / Showing Fear	Count	29	44	0	73
	% within CT	39.7%	60.3%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	4.9%	6.7%	0.0%	5.9%
Violence against Women	Count	0	25	0	25
	% within CT	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.0%	3.8%	0.0%	2.0%
Child Abuse	Count	1	0	0	1
	% within CT	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%
Rape	Count	1	0	0	1
	% within CT	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%
Attempt to Murder	Count	3	1	0	4
	% within CT	75.0%	25.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.5%	0.2%	0.0%	0.3%

Sexual Harassment	Count	1	33	0	34
	% within CT	2.9%	97.1%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.2%	5.0%	0.0%	2.7%
Hurt	Count	9	3	0	12
	% within CT	75.0%	25.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.5%	0.5%	0.0%	1.0%
Grievous Hurt	Count	6	1	0	7
	% within CT	85.7%	14.3%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.6%
Arson	Count	1	1	0	2
	% within CT	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%
Drug Related Offence	Count	25	7	0	32
	% within CT	78.1%	21.9%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	4.3%	1.1%	0.0%	2.6%
False Case	Count	3	1	0	4
	% within CT	75.0%	25.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.5%	0.2%	0.0%	0.3%
Land related lawsuit	Count	2	6	0	8
	% within CT	25.0%	75.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.3%	0.9%	0.0%	0.6%
Harassment by Police	Count	10	1	0	11
	% within CT	90.9%	9.1%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.7%	0.2%	0.0%	0.9%
Domestic Violence	Count	1	1	0	2
	% within CT	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	0.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%
Harassment	Count	11	2	0	13
	% within CT	84.6%	15.4%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.9%	0.3%	0.0%	1.0%
Assault	Count	7	1	0	8
	% within CT	87.5%	12.5%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within G	1.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.6%
Total	Count	586	659	1	1246
	% within CT	47.0%	52.9%	0.1%	100.0%
	% within G	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

1.3 City wise Victimization Information

Figure 3: Gender -Based Nature of Victimization

The prevalence of crime in Bangladesh has been diminished largely by the effective and active intervention of Bangladesh Police. The rate of victimization is quite less than in the previous decade. However, as a capital city of Bangladesh, Dhaka north city has a higher victimization rate than the other cities. Chattogram has the next highest victimization rate. Rangpur, which has newly declared as a city corporation in 2010, has stood at the third position here as it has the third-highest crime victimization record. Police statistics 2018 also support a higher tendency of crime in this city. The other big cities have a marginal and average rate of victimization, 5 percent. Rajshahi has the lowest victimization rate, with 3.8 percent. It should be noted here that the year 2018 remained highly intense for the national parliament election, which affected the crime rate all over the country.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.: City wise Victimization Percentage

City Name	Reported	Total	Population at 2011	Growth Rate	Projected Population	Reporting rate	Victimization rate (in 1 Lac)
Dhaka (South)	26	88	312374	1.315	410,771.81	6.33	21.42
Dhaka (North)	24	140	341939	1.315	449,649.79	5.34	31.14
Rajshahi	14	47	64534	1.104	71,245.54	19.65	65.97
Barisal	26	74	64008	0.989	63,303.91	41.07	116.90
Sylhet	15	65	84605	1.261	106,686.91	14.06	60.93
Khulna	27	78	99243	0.98	97,258.14	27.76	80.20
Mymensingh	30	94	65704	1.107	72,734.33	41.25	129.24
Rangpur	45	117	108687	1.104	119,990.45	37.50	97.51
Gazipur	26	86	87309	1.501	131,050.81	19.84	65.62
Chattogram	21	121	344365	1.118	385,000.07	5.45	31.43
Cumilla	15	88	48430	1.134	54,919.62	27.31	160.23
Bogura	25	102	91836	1.1	101,019.60	24.75	100.97
Tangail	10	55	39751	1.074	42,692.57	23.42	128.83
Narayanganj	20	91	141012	1.272	179,367.26	11.15	50.73
Total	324	1246	1893797	1.163	2,202,485.91	14.71	56.57

Table 3: Victimization Rate

Figure 5: Victimization Rate per 1 Lac in the Study Area

1.4 Spatial Aspects of Victimization and Analysis

About 95 percent of the respondents who became victims said they became victimized while living within their current address and only 5 percent while living at the last address before moving to the current address. In comparison to Town to the village, about 94 percent of the victims shared that the incident took place at the town while only 6 percent faced the incident in the village.

1.5 Place and Time of Victimization

1.5.1 Location-based Victimization Percentage:

Figure 6: Places where the Incidence Occurred

The study reveals that 52 percent of the victims got victimized at their own home or lodging, where theft alone constituted about 70 percent, and domestic violence constituted 5 percent, and the next highest number is 19 percent in the street. The survey data also shows that people also have faced mainly theft and also other forms of crime at the workplace (9 percent), at the public transportation (4 percent) where mainly theft constituted 36 percent and snatching 49 percent occurred, and at other places (5 percent) like educational institutions, parks, neighbours house, hospitals are the main areas and so on with various forms of crime.

1.5.2 Location vs. Gender:

The study shows that 58 percent of females became victims of theft crime while staying at home, while men constituted 42 percent. Men got more victimized (73 percent) than women at the workplace. Women, apart from theft, are more vulnerable to different forms of harassment and crimes on the street (about 18 percent) and public transportations (6 percent) than men.

1.5.3 The proximity of Place of Occurrence:

The places of occurrence were mostly closed to the residence of the victims. The average distance of the place of occurrences and residences was about 4.6 km, and the nearest police station from the place of occurrence was 3.3 km on an average.

1.5.4 Time vs. Victimization:

The time of crime occurrence is as vital as the place. As per the spatial aspects of crime, most crime occurrence needs a suitable target, motivated offender, and absence of guardian. These three elements are connected with location and time. Therefore, it could be said that time contributes a significant impact on the victimization. The study shows that most of the crimes have occurred within the mid hour of day time to the first hour of the night time, which starts from noon and ends 9 at night, and it constitutes 50 percent of the total crime. This study shows theft as the prevalent crime which occurred both at the home, workplace, and public transportations.

Figure 7: Time of Victimization

1.5.5 The month of Incident:

From January to April and November to December of 2018 found to be more crime-prone than the other months. In these months, theft has been prevalent, and some other property crimes also found as well.

Figure 8: Month at which Incident Occurred (n=1222)

8. Conclusion:

This study has explored the nature and extent of crime victimization in urban area in Bangladesh. The nature of crime victimization is depend on the various perspectives including victim perspectives (socio-demographic characteristics of offender), offender perspectives (socio-demographic characteristics of offender) and other perspectives that including spatial analysis of that occurrence, time and locations of the occurrence, types of offence, victim experiences with criminal justice system, gender based experience of that offence, city wise rate of occurrence etc. In this study, it is apparent that most of the victims are female who are married and housewife by their occupation, most of them were suffered from various types of offence including theft, sexual harassment, snatching, cheating, property related crime etc. Most of the victims faced theft where females account for 58% only for theft and 50% in all forms of crime. In Bangladesh, it is also found that Dhaka north city has a higher victimization rate than the other cities. Here, most of the respondents found victimized while they are living within their current address and the places of occurrence were mostly close to the residence of the victims. It is also found that most of the crimes have occurred within the mid hour of day time to the first hour of the night time, which starts from noon and ends at night. Most of the crime has occurred from January to April and November to December of 2018.

From the summary of the findings of the study, it can be said that victimization survey is most effective because it reveal the root level explanations of crime occurrences and reasons of victimization and also indicate the how and why an offence is occurred, when and where an offence is occurred. It also explained the socio demographic characteristics of victims and offenders that also help to identify the habitant offender and possible victim. But there are limited survey are held in Bangladesh. Like United States, there are no any Uniform Crime Report (UCR) and National Crime Victimization Survey (NCVS) program in Bangladesh. But in recent time, various victimization surveys are held for upheld the nature of crime victimization in Bangladesh. Crime victimization survey in selected urban areas of Bangladesh, 2019 is a recent example of victimization survey that helps to explain the nature and extent of crime victimization in urban area. At last it can be said, crime victimization survey or study can aware Criminal Justice system to reduce crime and to make aware public about these crimes being occurred and it is necessary that government should more focus on crime victimization survey or study for reducing victimization in urban area in Bangladesh.

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